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LAM-Chat

A Fault-Tolerant Chatting Application

AHMED SALAH TAWFIK IBRAHIM

Leena Aizdi

Morteza Arezoumandan

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1. Introduction

Although we live in a global bubble nowadays, people are getting more and more disconnected from one another and they live in this virtual world offered by lots of online services. That is why it is sometimes difficult to find someone to talk to from within one's own circle of friends or family; therefore, there is this need of creating more and more chatting services that are preferably anonymous which would eventually allow people to communicate with one another without worries or constraints. LAM-Chat is the solution we offer to allow users to communicate anonymously and we will be describing it in more detail in the following sections. The implementation of this application can be found through this link:

<https://github.com/m-arezoumandan/LAM-Chat>

2. Requirements

LAM-Chat implements a set of functional requirements (section 2.1) while respecting some constraints which are the non-functional requirements (section 2.2). In section 2.3, we show a use case diagram that summarizes the functionalities implemented in LAM-Chat.

2.1: Functional Requirements

Our application has just one actor which is the user and the user should be allowed to perform the following functionalities:

- 1) Create a chat room
- 2) Join an existing chat room
- 3) Specify a unique username for themselves
- 4) Write messages on the room
- 5) View the online users on the room
- 6) Write private messages to any user on the room
- 7) Receive messages sent by other users on the room
- 8) Receive private messages sent by other users to him/her
- 9) Leave the chat room

2.2: Non-Functional Requirements

We put the following constraints in mind while designing the application:

- 1) Fault tolerance: our application should be able to operate in faulty settings, for example, if the server is down, it should be able to pick up the work from where it left it.
- 2) Usability: our application should have a user-friendly interface even if there is no GUI.
- 3) Concurrency: the application should be multi-threaded and users should be able to send and receive messages concurrently.
- 4) Minimal Storage: the application should not use any sort of persistent storage and it should use the minimum amount of memory to perform the tasks.

- 5) Synchronization: each client should be in sync with the server by receiving acknowledgements before being able to proceed with other tasks.

2.3: Use-case Diagram

3. Implementation

The application was developed using Java and Erlang. The dependencies in the java project were managed through maven and the communication between Java and Erlang was handled through the Jinterface. In the following section, we will be describing the main classes of our application (section 3.1), the architecture of our application (section 3.2) which includes the way we implemented the server to handle the functional requirements (section 3.2.1) and the implementation of the client (section 3.2.2) and how we implemented the non-functional requirements (sections 3.3 through 3.7).

3.1: Class Diagram

The entities that we had in our application to handle the logic and storage, especially at the client side, were the user, the room and the message. The user class

contains the needed information about the user which includes the username, which is a unique identifier for the user within the room, and the status flag which indicates whether the user is online or offline. The message class encapsulates the concept of a message and it has two attributes which are the content and the date. Obviously, there is a relationship between the user and the message that is one-to-many. Finally, the room class abstracts the concept of a chatroom and it just has the name of the room as an identifier of the room. There exists a one-to-many relationship between the room and the user and between the room and the message. It is worth noting that a room can have no messages at all but it must have at least one user. Consequently, a user can send no messages or as many as he/she wants. All of this is illustrated in the following class diagram.

3.2 System Architecture

Our system was designed following the client-server architecture because we allow the communication between the different clients only through the server. The server accepts different messages from the client side and performs an action accordingly and this is described in detail in section 3.2.1. As for the client, it contains the necessary data structures that would enable it to store messages locally and it serves as a container for an abstract user within a chatroom and the details of this are

described in section 3.2.2. The following diagram is a general overview of our system architecture which will become clearer after the following two subsections.

3.2.1: Server

As mentioned above, the server's job is to receive different messages from the different clients and it should perform an action based on the received message. The server was written purely in erlang using the `gen_server` behavior because it provides fast response and it is well suited for our message passing model. It is also thread safe and so there are no race conditions when more than one process tries to modify something. Our server consists mainly of a loop and a simple list that keeps track of

the current room and users (more on that in section 3.3). The loop waits until a message is received by the server. There are different types of messages that the server can get which are listed below:

1) {newuser}:

This message is sent by the advertiser process in the client to let the server know that a new client is trying to use the application. The server sends back a list of available chat rooms to this advertiser process.

2) {From, connect, Room, Username}

This message is sent by the advertiser process as well to ask the server to let the user identified by the Username variable to join the room specified by the Room variable. The server checks the list of usernames in the chatroom and if the Username does not match any existing username, then the server adds the user to the chat room and sends to the advertiser process a list of currently online users in the room. It also informs all the other users of the presence of the new user. If there is a match between one of the usernames and Username, however, then the server sends to the advertiser a message indicating that the username is taken and it does not add the user to the room.

3) {From, clientListen, User, Room}

This message is sent by the receiver process in the client to the server to let the server know that it is accepting messages on the pid specified by the From variable.

4) {send, Msg, User, room, Room}

This message is sent by the sender process in the client to let the server send the text message specified by Msg on the room specified by Room. The server then forwards this message to all the client receiver processes of all the users in the chat room.

5) {send, Msg, Sender, user, User}

This message is sent by the sender process in the client to let the server send the text message specified by Msg to the user specified by User. The server then forwards this message to the client receiver process of that user.

6) {exit, From, Room, User}

This message is sent by the advertiser process to let the server know that the user specified by User has left the room specified by Room. The server then removes

this user from the list and forwards to all the receiver processes of all the users in the room that this user has left.

3.2.2: Client

The client is a way to encapsulate the behavior of a user within a chat room as mentioned above. It contains the user object as well as the chat room object to keep track locally of all the messages sent on the chat room and to also keep track of the currently online users in the room. It also contains the needed structures to construct a client node that is able to communicate with the server. Any given client node has three main processes; the advertiser, the sender and the receiver. The advertiser's job is to inform the server of the presence or the absence of the user that is hosted on that client node. It also constructs the chat room locally upon receiving from the server that the client is added to the room. It does this by creating the list of online users and by setting up the room name locally. The sender's job, however, is to send a message to the server containing something to be sent either to the room or to a certain user in the room. As for the receiver, all it does is that it tells the server where to send messages to the user hosted on the client node and then it starts receiving those messages upon their arrival. The advertiser process starts with the creation of the client node and it terminates when the user is successfully removed from the room when he/she leaves the room. The receiver process starts immediately after the client is accepted by the server and it is terminated once the user leaves the chat room. The sender process, however, starts once the user decides to send a message and it terminates upon receiving a confirmation message from the server.

3.3: Storage

Since we wanted to keep the storage to a minimum, we decided to avoid using a database in our server. Instead, we decided that it is enough to keep a list that contains tuples of the form {Room, User, From} where Room is the room name and User is the username and From is the address of the receiver process of the client. This is also better for our case since we are not expecting so many users to be using our application at the same time, so a list of tuples is convenient to keep track of the users

and rooms currently available. It is also efficient because we don't have to keep track of empty chat rooms because whenever a room has no users, it gets deleted from the server because when a user is deleted, the tuple containing that user is also deleted and so the room will not be present in any of the tuples if it has no users. We also keep a copy of that list on the backup server. It is probably better to create a persistent storage to keep this list in case of complete failure of all nodes, but this is kept for future versions of the application.

On the client side, however, we keep track of the messages sent to the chat room locally at each client node in a list of messages. In this way, we have message history within the session which means that once a user leaves the room, he/she will not be able to view any previous messages because the list will be flushed.

3.4: Fault Tolerance

Since we are working in a distributed environment, faults are inevitable and that is why it was necessary to handle them in a proper way. We assume that we have only one server that provides the service to all the clients and so, when this server is down, we need to make sure that the information stored on that server is not lost. In other words, our goal is to make the server pick up from where it has left the work. This is achieved through the supervisor node which restarts the server upon its failure so that the server can restart itself by restoring the list of tuples from the backup node. First, the server will be sending any modification to the backup node. Then, upon failure, the supervisor will restart the server which then sends a recovery message to the backup node which, in turn, replies back to the server with the list of clients. In that way, the application will continue to work despite the failure of the server.

3.5: Concurrency

In the java clients, we use multiple threads that run concurrently. Mainly, we have the sender and the receiver processes which run concurrently which was explained in detail earlier.

3.6: Synchronization

While Erlang has asynchronous message passing built in as part of the language, it is still possible to implement synchronous calls. The way to have synchronous message passing is to implement something akin to an acknowledgement. In the application, synchronous calls to the server are managed by using the `gen_server` module. The `gen_server` library module has a number of mechanisms and safeguards built in that function behind the scene. For calling the server in a synchronous manner, `gen_server:call/2` is used. It sends a synchronous message to the server and waits for a **Reply** while the server handles the request in a callback function. The **Reply** as the return value to the call. In the server, the `handle_call/3` callback function handles the request. Using `handle_call` will block the process for the duration of the call. The client node will be blocked until it receives the acknowledgement from the server.

4. User Manual

4.1: Package Organization

The code is organized into two main folders, the java folder and the erlang folder. Inside the erlang folder there is the server module (`server.erl`), the backup server module (`backup.erl`) and the supervisor (`server_sup.erl`) and inside the java folder there is one package (`it.unipi.lam`) which should ideally contain two packages. One of them should be a client package and the other is the entities package. The client package contains the `Client` class which implements the functions of a client node which are mainly the send and receive functions. These functions construct and decode messages for the client to understand. It also contains the `ClientSender` and `ClientReceiver` classes which are the sender and receiver threads and they invoke the client send and receive functions. Finally, there is the `LAM` class which is the driver class and it also contains the advertiser process. As for the entities package, it contains the class `User` which encapsulates the user entity described in section 3.1, the class `Message` which encapsulates the message entity described in section 3.1 and the class

Room which encapsulates the room entity described in section 3.1. The following screenshot illustrates this structure:

4.2: Running the server

The server should be run through the erlang shell. First of all, the shell needs to be renamed and the name of the server mailbox should be modified in the LAM class of the client. This is done through running this command on a linux terminal “erl -sname server”. After that, the backup module and the server_sup module need to be compiled through the following commands “c(backup).” and “c(server_sup).”. Then, the backup server should be started through the command “backup:start_link()”. Finally, the supervisor should be started by running “server_sup:start_link()”.

4.3: Running the client

The client can be started through the main method of the LAM class but it will work only if the server mailbox in LAM matches the name of the server shell. Then there is a set of commands which the user can use to interact with the application:

- 1) x: leave the application if not in any chat room or leave the chat room
- 2) send: send a message ---> r: to a room, p: private message
- 3) show: show the users in the room